

Alternatives to Vehicle Routing Planning Through Exact and Approximate Methods

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Abstract: Nowadays, businesses believe in the importance of logistics to increase customer satisfaction and economic revenues. One of the most important aspects within Supply Chain Management (SCM) is distribution planning. For this, routing and network models are frequently used. However, as the number of locations to be served within a network increases, so is its complexity. In such cases, special methods and software are needed to provide the best solutions while being able to cope with the complexity of the problem within reasonable time. In this work two solving alternatives are explored for the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP), which is one of the most important routing planning models with the logistic field. These alternatives consist of an evolutionary metaheuristic and an exact method, and their suitability are assessed by considering the quality of the solutions (routes of minimum distance or cost) and computational time. The advantages, disadvantages, similarities and differences between these methods are analyzed, providing support for their use within the decision-making processes of a case study.

Keywords: Distribution Route Planning, Travelling Salesman Problem, TSP, Genetic Algorithms, Branch & Bound

I. INTRODUCTION

Currently, successful companies are constantly looking for improvements, particularly within their logistic operations, always seeking to be more competitive in the market and be more profitable while minimizing their costs. For companies which have their own transportation fleet, they have greater opportunities and control to improve their delivery times and costs. Making good logistics routing planning requires efficient technological tools. Hence, in order to offer better response times to their clients while generating better profits for the company, they must consider specialized technological tools [1]. In practice, many companies plan their distribution routes by empirical experience, sometimes based only on the drivers' experience. This cannot reflect an optimal distribution, due to the lack of necessary information for good analysis and decision-making process. Currently, route design has become a source of competitive advantages for companies that have experienced this situation. This is because up to 50% of the companies' total annual logistic costs are attributed to distribution.

What may be the best option depends of the case study, and the balance between accuracy and time performance of the solution method. In this work we analyze both, approximate and exact methods for a case study. Implementation of both methods is described in the following sections and the results are discussed.

II. BACKGROUND

Transportation is an important factor because it involves tracing the route where the raw material must pass through to reach the manufacturing plant, or the route where the finished product must pass through to reach the end customer. There are different ways of modeling the way of transporting products, one of them is the Traveling Salesman Problem (TSP) [2]. Dantzig, Fulkerson and Johnson modeled the problem with linear integer programming and developed a method to solve small instances to optimality [3].

The TSP may be symmetrical, where the distance from location A to location B is equal from B to A, and it can be asymmetrical if the distance from A to B is different from B to A. The number of possible routes in a network is

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determined by the equation: $(n-1)!$. Hence, just for 10 locations there are $9! = 362,880$ ways to visit them. This number increases exponentially as n increases. This represents a challenge for larger instances. Thus, the TSP has given origin to multiple initiatives to improve efficiency in route determination.

In computational terms, the TSP is classified as a NP-hard problem. These issues are handled by computational complexity theory, which classifies problems as NP-hardness and NP-complete problems, the difference between "feasible" and "intractable" is based on the time that an algorithm could take to give a solution to a problem with n objects [4]. For this reason, finding all possible routes is extremely inefficient and impossible for large networks. While there are algorithms that can provide optimal solutions, such as the Branch & Bound method (which works the problem as an allocation algorithm and solves it using the simplex method) [5], it can only provide solutions within short time for small instances.

On the other hand, the closest neighbor algorithm, cheapest and two-way insertion heuristics have been developed to solve the TSP approximately within short times. Approximate algorithms such as Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are based on the evolutionary and reproductive concepts of Darwin's theory, attempting to imitate the natural process of the evolution of living beings [6]. GAs evolve a population of individuals, in our case possible solutions, subjecting them to random combinations that resemble those of biological evolution processes, deciding the most adaptable combinations to the environment in question, in this case, which route is a better option to minimize costs. Some characteristics of GAs are the following [7]:

- Better adapted individuals are more likely to reproduce (good solutions can create other good solutions).
- The least adapted also have possibilities to reproduce (solutions of low quality can be omitted from the search space).
- Given both parents, the offspring gene is obtained as a random combination of the parents' genes (solutions are obtained from partial integration of the different parts of two "parent" solutions).

In this work a GA is proposed as the approximate method and performance is compared with the exact method of Branch & Bound.

III. MATHEMATICAL MODEL OF THE TSP

The TSP is one of the most used and studied problems in logistics [8]. The TSP consists of finding a route that is the shortest among the location nodes, considering that each of these can be visited only once, before arriving at the new starting point, seeking to minimize the cost of travel, distance, or time [3]. Figure 1 presents the visualization of a Hamiltonian Circuit, which is a common TSP solution.

Fig. 1 Example of a TSP solution (own work).

Then, the TSP mathematical model proposed by Dantzig is presented as follows:

Objective Function

$$\text{Minimize } \sum_{(i,j) \in E} C_{ij} X_{i,j} \tag{1}$$

Subject to

$$\sum_{j \in \Delta^+(i)} X_{ijk} = 1 \quad \forall i \in V \tag{2}$$

$$\sum_{j \in \Delta^-(i)} X_{ijk} = 1 \quad \forall i \in V \tag{3}$$

$$\sum_{i \in S, j \in \Delta^+(i) \setminus S} X_{ijk} \geq 1 \quad \forall S \subset V \tag{4}$$

$$X_{ij} \in \{0,1\} \quad \forall (i,j) \in E \tag{5}$$

The binary variables x_{ij} indicate whether the arc (i, j) is used in the solution. The objective function (1) establishes that the total cost of the solution is the sum of the costs of the arcs used. Restrictions (2) and (3) indicate that the route must arrive and leave each node exactly once. Finally, restrictions (4) are called sub-tour deletion constraints and indicate that every sub-set of S -nodes must be abandoned at least once. Finally, (5) represents the binary nature of the decision variable x_{ij} .

IV. APPROXIMATE METHOD – GENETIC ALGORITHM

GAs operate on a population of K initial solutions that are randomly generated, called individuals. For each individual $i \in K$, a function is defined that assesses its adaptability to the environment, that is, how optimal is for the solution, so that the more adaptable it is, the better solution it represents [9]. At each iteration, evolutionary operators are applied on these “parent” solution to combine and modify them to obtain “offspring” solutions, thus creating a new population (reproduction processes of crossover and mutation). Selection operators are probabilistic and give privileges to the individuals with the greatest adaptability in the population [9].

Once the new “offspring” population is generated, the initial population is updated with the best T individuals. Figure 2 presents the steps of our GA implementation.

Fig. 2 Steps of the GA (own work)

The implementation of the GA was performed through the programming platform GNU Octave. The following main functions were coded for the GA:

- The input data consists of a square matrix $N \times N$ with the distance C_{ij} between each point i and j to be visited by the

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vehicle. In total, there are N location points, hence, $i, j = 1, \dots, N$. This was obtained by the Google Maps® tool.

- An initial population of size K is created where each individual consists of the permutation (sequence) of $N+1$ location points.
- The fitness is the cumulative sum of distances of visiting the location points as stated by the sequence of the permutation.
- The initial population is sorted from lowest to highest fitness value (total cumulative distance).
- A total of X and Y new solution are obtained by crossover and mutation operators respectively. For crossover the Cycle Crossover (CX) and the Partially Matched Crossover (PMX) were considered. For mutation, the random exchange of three and five locations were considered.
- Selection of parents is performed by tournament (parents are selected randomly from the best P individuals, where $P < K$).
- Two different parent solutions are needed to create two offspring solution by crossover.
- One parent solution is needed to create a single offspring by mutation.
- The fitness data is obtained for the X and Y offspring solutions created by crossover and mutation.
- An integrated solution with the initial population (K) and the offspring populations (X, Y) is created. Sorting from lowest to highest fitness value is performed. Finally, the best K individuals are kept to update the initial population.
- The process is repeated L times ($L = 200$ iterations).

V. EXACT METHOD

The Lingo® software was used to solve the routing problem to optimality for comparison. To use this tool, the following steps were performed:

- Determine the variables x_{ij} .
- Define the objective function (minimization) and cost metrics (symmetric/asymmetric distance matrix).
- Define the restrictions.

For the exact method, this linear programming tool considered the Branch & Bound (B-and-B) method.

VI. BUSINESS CASE STUDY

The business considered for this analysis was a company that supplies convenience products for 22 different restaurants (in total there are 23 locations as the supplier's location must be considered). This company must organize its distribution route to satisfy all its customers within the shortest time (dependent of distance travelled).

The GA was configured as follows: $K = 500$ individuals, $X = 200$ and $Y = 50$. Table 1 presents the results of the GA and the B-and-B methods. The distance difference between both is approximately 42.44 kilometers, which leads to an error of 4.9%. In contrast the time of the B-and-B is significantly larger when compared to the GA method.

Table 1 Comparison of Results: Exact vs. Approximate Methods

	Lingo®	GA (Octave Implementation)
Objective Function	866.7	909.14
Time to Best Solution	72:00:00 h	00:11:08 h
Error Gap (%)	-	$(909.14-866.7)/866.7 = 0.049$

VII. CONCLUSIONS

According to the results achieved with the two methods, both solutions are useful. While the optimal solution is always desired, sometimes achieving it may require unreasonable time. In this case, it took 72 hours for the software to achieve the optimal solution. In contrast, the GA found a very suitable solution within 11 minutes, with an error gap of 4.9%.

Having fast solutions with a minimum error is always welcomed in the absence on an exact solution which would require a significant amount of time. However, no method is better than the other, each one has application according to the size of the instance, solution time, costs and specific needs of the company.

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